

Review Article

Aquatic Exposure to Nanoparticles: Fish as Bio indicators of Potential Human Health Hazards

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ARTICLE INFO

Published: 06 May, 2026

Keywords:

Nanotoxicology; Zinc oxide nanoparticles; Fish gills; Histopathology; Oxidative stress; LC₅₀; Human health risk

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.20050255

ABSTRACT

The growing utilization of Zinc oxide nanoparticles (ZnO -NPs) in industrial, environmental and biomedical areas has elicited fear regarding their possible toxic impact on aquatic organisms and human health. The current study assesses the acute toxicity and histological modification caused by ZnO nanoparticles in the freshwater fish *Trichopodus trichopterus*. The acute toxicity (96 h LC 50) was measured using various concentration of nanoparticles succeeded by sublethal exposure experiments conducted to assess alterations at the tissue level. The results indicated a concentration dependent rise in mortality, yielding LC50 value 20.44 mg/L. Microscopic analysis of gill tissue showed significant changes such as epithelial hyperplasia, lamellar fusion, necrosis, aneurism, and disorganization of normal structure. These alterations suggest oxidative stress led toxicity. Taking into consideration functional similarities between fish gills and human lungs, these findings raise the potential threat of nanoparticles to human health. Thus, these findings emphasize the importance of fish as bioindicators in nanotoxicology and the need for appropriate regulation of nanoparticle discharge into water.

INTRODUCTION

The creation and use of tailored nanoparticles in a variety of scientific and industrial domains have greatly expanded due to the speedy development of nanotechnology. This is because of their distinctive physicochemical characteristics, such as high surface reactivity, large surface area, and

varied functional potential, metal and metal oxide nanoparticles in particular have attracted a lot of attention (Asghar *et al.*, 2015). These qualities make them ideal for use in biomedical sciences, electronics, catalysis, and environmental clean-up. Zinc oxide (ZnO) nanoparticles have emerged as especially important among the other nanomaterials due to their properties that can be

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Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

regulated by manipulating the size and shape of the particles. ZnO nanoparticles have been extensively explored for diverse technological applications, including antimicrobial treatments, magnetic systems, electronic devices, catalysis, drug delivery, water purification, air filtration, and photocatalytic degradation of pollutants and hazardous dyes (S. Chakrabarti and B. Dutta, 2004). In addition to these industrial uses, their multifunctional properties have enabled their application in biological and medical fields such as biosensing, bioimaging, gene delivery, targeted drug delivery, and nanomedicine (Rasmussen *et al.*, 2010). Furthermore, ZnO nanoparticles are widely used as antimicrobial agents in products such as ointments, lotions, mouthwashes, and surface coatings to inhibit microbial growth (Jones *et al.*, 2008). They are also utilized as dietary supplements in humans and livestock, as zinc plays a crucial role in enhancing immune function and exerting anti-inflammatory effects (Prasad, 2008; Rincker *et al.*, 2005). However, the rapid expansion of nanotechnology-based industries has led to the continuous release of engineered nanoparticles into the environment, particularly into aquatic ecosystems. According to the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), ZnO nanoparticles are considered priority nanomaterials of environmental concern due to their high production volume and widespread applications (Lai *et al.*, 2023). Numerous studies have investigated the toxicological effects of ZnO nanoparticles, particularly in mammalian cell lines (Yang *et al.*, 2009; Xia *et al.*, 2008). These studies indicate that ZnO nanoparticles can induce oxidative stress through the generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS), leading to cellular damage, disruption of enzymatic activities, and structural alterations in tissues and macromolecules (Boudou, A. and Ribeyre, F., 1997). More over, exposure to ZnO nanoparticles has been related with histopathological changes in vital organs such

as the gills, liver, and kidneys. Fish are widely recognized as effective bioindicators for assessing environmental contamination due to their sensitivity to pollutants and their ecological relevance. Among fish organs, the gills represent a critical interface between the organism and its surrounding environment, as they are directly exposed to waterborne contaminants. Structurally and functionally, fish gills share similarities with the lung epithelium (Handy *et al.*, 2008), including a large surface area, thin epithelial lining, and direct interaction with the external environment. This resemblance provides a valuable model for understanding respiratory toxicity and predicting potential human health risks. ZnO nanoparticles are known to generate reactive oxygen species, which can cause epithelial damage, inflammation, and impairment of normal physiological functions in both aquatic organisms and mammalian systems (Oberdörster *et al.*, 2005). Therefore, histopathological alterations observed in fish gills can serve as an important indicator for assessing nanoparticle-induced toxicity and may provide insights into potential respiratory and systemic effects in humans. In this context, the present study aims to evaluate the acute toxicity (LC₅₀) of ZnO nanoparticles and to investigate their dose-dependent histopathological effects on the gills of the freshwater fish *Trichopodus trichopterus*. The results obtained from the current study will be instrumental in increasing the knowledge about the toxicity of nanoparticles in the aquatic environment and help to understand their possible implications on environmental and human safety.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Chemicals and Nanoparticle Preparation

Zinc oxide nanoparticles (ZnO-NPs) (< 20 nm) were synthesized following the method reported in our earlier study (Chandak *et al.*, 2026). In our previous work, physical and chemical

characterization of ZnO-NPs was performed. Stock suspensions of ZnO-NPs were prepared in distilled water and sonicated (40 kHz, 100 W) for 30 minutes before treatment to ensure uniform dispersion of the nanoparticles.

2.2. Experimental Animals and Maintenance

Healthy adult specimens of *Trichopodus trichopterus* (average length: 7.60 ± 0.09 cm; weight: 7.90 ± 0.15 g) were collected from a local source. Fish were acclimatized under laboratory conditions for two weeks prior to experimentation in dechlorinated tap water. During acclimation, fish were maintained in aerated glass aquaria under controlled conditions (temperature: $24.18 \pm 0.14^\circ\text{C}$; pH: 7.4 ± 0.06 ; dissolved oxygen: 4.8 ± 0.19 mg/L) with a 12:12 h light-dark cycle. Fish were fed a standard commercial diet and dried worms ad libitum. All experimental procedures were conducted in accordance with CPCSEA guidelines, New Delhi.

2.3. Acute toxicity Assessment (96 h LC₅₀)

Acute toxicity of ZnO-NPs was assessed by exposing fish to a range of concentrations (0, 1, 2.5, 5, 7.5, 10, 12.5, 15, 17.5, 20, and 25 mg/L) under static conditions for 96 hours. Ten fish were employed at each concentration. Sonication was conducted for 30 minutes prior to treatment to keep the suspension homogeneous. Fish were not fed during the exposure period in order to prevent nanoparticle adsorption to feed and feces. Mortality was recorded at 12-hour intervals, and dead fish were removed to avoid contamination.

2.4. Sublethal Exposure Study

During the experiment for sub chronic toxicity testing, fishes were kept for 14 days under semi-static condition in the presence of sub lethal concentration of ZnO-NPs at doses of 1, 5, and 10 mg/L. Control fishes, without any nanoparticle

treatment, were also maintained. Six fishes per group were used (n=18) and the experiment was conducted in three replicates.

2.5. Histopathological Examination

Fish were randomly chosen at the end of the exposure period and sacrificed for histological analysis. Gill samples were dissected from the fish and were placed in Bouin's fixative for 24 hours. Afterwards, the specimens underwent a dehydration process via graded series of ethanol, cleared in xylene, and embedded in paraffin wax. Sections of approximately 8 μm thickness were cut with rotary microtome and stained using hematoxylin and eosin (H&E). Histological observations were carried out using a Zeiss Primo Star microscope equipped with an Axiocam 105 digital camera.

2.6. Statistical Analysis

LC₅₀ value was determined after 96 hours via Probit analysis and was reported at 95% confidence limits. Data were reported as mean \pm SEM. Differences between treated and control group were statistically analyzed with ANOVA coupled with Dunnett test for a value of $p < 0.05$. Statistical analysis was done with SPSS version 20 and Graphpad Prism software.

3. Results and Discussion

The present study demonstrates that exposure to zinc oxide nanoparticles (ZnO-NPs) induces significant toxic effects in *Trichopodus trichopterus* under controlled laboratory conditions. Water quality parameters remained stable throughout the experimental period, ensuring that the observed effects were primarily due to nanoparticle exposure. A clear concentration-dependent increase in mortality was recorded, with a 96 h LC₅₀ value (Table 1 and

figure 1) of 20.44 mg/L, indicating moderate toxicity of ZnO nanoparticles to the test species. The LC₅₀ value obtained in this study is consistent with previously reported findings in different fish species, although variations have been observed depending on species sensitivity, nanoparticle

size, and exposure conditions (Saha *et al.*, 2022; Aziz *et al.*, 2020; Asghar *et al.*, 2015). Such variability highlights the importance of species-specific evaluation in nanotoxicological studies.

Fish species	MeO-NPs	LC50	95% CI (LCL–UCL)	Lethal conc.	95% CI (LCL–UCL)	Pearson Goodness Fit		
						Chi-Square	DF	P-value
<i>Trichopodus trichopterus</i>	ZnO-NPs	20.44	12.98–69.41	76.3mg/L	39.020–2716.904	1.564	6	0.995

Table1.LC 50 Fish acute toxicity of ZnO NPs (mg/L)

CI, confidence interval (mg/L); LCL, lower confidence limit (mg/L); UCL, upper confidence

interval (mg/L); Lethal Conc., lethal concentrations (mg/L); Df, Degree of freedom

Figure 1. 96 h percent mortality and probit mortality of *T. trichopterus* exposed to ZnO NPs

Histopathological examination (Figure.2) revealed that control fish (fig. A-B) exhibited normal gill architecture with well-organized primary and secondary lamellae. In contrast, fish exposed to ZnO-NPs (fig. C-E) showed significant pathological alterations, including epithelial hyperplasia, thickening of the epithelial lining, lamellar fusion, necrosis, aneurism, and

disorganization of lamellar structures. These changes are indicative of impaired respiratory efficiency and disruption of osmoregulatory functions. Similar observations have been reported in earlier studies, where nanoparticle exposure resulted in structural damage to gill tissues (Subashkumar and Selvanayagam, 2014; Suganthi *et al.*, 2015; Kaya *et al.*, 2016; Shazad *et al.*, 2018).

Figure. 2. Histology of gill (A-B) Gill tissue of control fish (C-E) Gill exposed to different conc. of ZnO NPs for 14 days. SGL-secondary gill lamellae, PGL-primary gill lamellae, GA-gill arch, C- cartilage, PC-pillar cells. PVC-pavement cell, BC-blood capillaries, LF-lamellar fusion, N-necrosis, DL- distorted lamellae

Figure. 3. Effect of ZnO NPs on SGL length and width of *T. trichopterus* exposed to ZnO NPs for 14 days

The observed histological damage may be attributed to oxidative stress induced by ZnO nanoparticles, leading to cellular injury and tissue degeneration. The reduction in the length and width of secondary lamellae (Figure. 3) further supports the occurrence of morphological and functional impairment. Fish gills are highly sensitive to environmental contaminants due to their direct exposure to the aquatic environment, making them reliable indicators of waterborne toxicity. The histopathological alterations observed in this study reinforce the use of gill tissues as effective biomarkers for environmental contamination (Au, 2004; Fernandes *et al.*, 2007). Importantly, the toxic effects observed in fish models have broader implications beyond aquatic systems. The ability of nanoparticles to induce oxidative stress, epithelial damage, and tissue dysfunction suggests potential risks to higher organisms, including humans, upon exposure. Therefore, fish-based toxicity studies provide valuable insights into nanoparticle-induced biological effects and contribute to the evaluation of potential risks to human health

CONCLUSION:

This study revealed that zinc oxide nanoparticles have strong toxic effect on *T. trichopterus*. This reflected higher mortality rates and histopathological damage in the gills as the concentration of nanoparticles increases. The observed changes, such as epithelial hyperplasia, lamellar fusion, necrosis, aneurism, and overall structural disruption suggest serious impairment of respiratory and osmoregulatory functions. These results highlight the ecological dangers posed by nanoparticles pollution in aquatic ecosystem which can indirectly reflected in food chain. Nanoparticles pollution in aquatic ecosystems confirm that fish gills are sensitive and reliable indicators of environmental stress. Moreover, the gill damage observed after nanoparticle exposure indicates that these fish models could help predict potential respiratory and systemic toxicity of nanoparticles in humans. Overall, the findings emphasize the need for careful monitoring and regulation of nanoparticles release into aquatic environments and add to the growing

understanding of their effects on both ecosystems and human.

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HOW TO CITE: Aditi Chandak, Vikas Barsagade, Trupti Khedkar*, Aquatic Exposure to Nanoparticles: Fish as Bio indicators of Potential Human Health Hazards, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2026, Vol 4, Issue 5, 1051-1058. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20050255>

